

CHALLENGES IN DECISION-MAKING AUTONOMY IN ROMANIAN PRESCHOOLS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: AN EXPLORATORY SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Purpose – *The present study aimed to review the published findings related to the challenges in decision-making autonomy in Romanian preschool settings during the Covid-19 pandemic. Our question was the following: „What do we know about the challenges in decision-making autonomy in Romanian preschools during the Covid-19 pandemic?”*

Methodology/approach - *We followed the guidelines for a systematic review (though we proposed an exploratory, narrative view). We consulted four databases, i.e., Google Scholar, Eric, DOAJ, and Science Direct. The Key-terms that we used were the following: Covid-19 + management + decision + preschool + Romania.*

Findings – *Our research findings proposed 109 research articles that aligned with the proposed criteria. Out of these studies, none of them addressed our research question.*

Research limitations/implications *Our research highlights the scarce evidence concerning the challenges in decision-making autonomy in Romanian preschools during the Covid-19 pandemic.*

Practical implications – *our results call for further research on this matter, especially considering the challenges and effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on other different management fields, such as the medical domain, environmental nanotechnology, ergonomics, and health.*

Originality/value – *Our research explores the management -related challenges and opportunities in a post-pandemic reality, highlighting that extensive research is needed to better understand and manage the various and complex challenges managers of preschool education settings face in the context of covid-19 pandemic*

Key words: *decision; COVID-19; autonomy.*

Introduction

Decision-making is a manager's main activity, and all the other activities are carried out to ensure that the decision has already been taken to implement and monitor its effectiveness. Furthermore, managers must decide when and to what extent they will involve their subordinates in decision-making, as employee involvement determines the quality of the decision-making act and the degree of participation in the application of decisions (Lunenburg, 2010). In an educational setting (specifically, in the Romanian education system), the management is manifested at the following levels: top management (i.e., leadership level); middle management (i.e., level of commissions/departments/compartments), and operational management (i.e., level of preschool/parent groups) (Håkansson, 2016).

Top managers, i.e., kindergarten principals, establish objectives, strategies, and policies, represent the organization concerning the central and local administration, being responsible for the overall process processes of the organization. In addition, they engage in developing long-term plans, guiding their kindergarten's future activities. Also, they establish the objectives and strategy at the global level of the organization to facilitate and stimulate the kindergarten's adaptation to change. To ensure quality strategic management, the director must exceed the status of the manager and fulfill the leading role.

However, the Covid-19 pandemic brought major changes to the educational systems and, implicitly, to the management processes and decision-making autonomy in all educational institutions, including preschool units. In addition to adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 schools and kindergartens closure (König et al., 2020), managers from the education sector had to rethink the communication and decision-making processes, facing various challenges in this regard (Msila, 2021).

The present study

The present study aimed to investigate the findings related to Challenges in decision-making autonomy in Romanian preschool settings during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, we aimed to perform a narrative review on the results published in this area from March 2020 until May 2022. Therefore, our question was the following: *What do we know about the challenges in decision-making autonomy in Romanian preschools during the Covid-19 pandemic?*

To answer this question, we explored the published research in this area, using the PRISMA (2020) guidelines for a systematic review. The review or systematic review is a critical evaluation that is carried out using systematic methods proposed/developed to minimize errors and to combine the existing evidence on a specific topic (in the present case – PRISMA). However, this was an exploratory approach, aiming to serve as a future starting point for future, extended investigations.

Research procedure

We followed the guidelines (PRISMA, 2020) for a systematic review (though we proposed an exploratory, narrative view). We consulted four databases, i.e., Google Scholar, Eric, DOAJ, and Science Direct. The Key-terms that we used were the following: Covid-19 + management + decision + preschool + Romania. We also used these *additional inclusion criteria*: (1) Language: English; Type: Research Articles; Publishing timeline: 2020-2022.

Results

Following the consultation of the proposed databases, the results revealed a total of 109 research articles. Out of these articles, 102 results were revealed from the Google Scholar Database, 7 results were revealed following the consultation of the Science Direct Database, while the two other databases revealed no further results (i.e., DOAJ and ERIC). Thus, our research findings proposed 109 research articles that aligned with the proposed criteria. Out of these studies, none of them addressed our research question. Despite the initial number of records found (n=109), most studies focused on the mental health of children during the pandemic, coping and stress, associated diseases (e.g., Gao et al., 2022), vaccine acceptance/hesitancy (e.g., Torracinta et al., 2021), resilience (e.g., Manchia et al., 2022).

Discussion

The present findings related to education mainly were associated with teachers' satisfaction, digital literacy (e.g., Li et al., 2022), socio-emotional competence (e.g., Lozano-Peña et al., 2021), or digital technology (e.g., Haleem et al., 2022). However, some studies referred to decision processes when discussing preschool settings by referring to the experiences and challenges of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic from educators' point of view (Faridah et al., 2021), coping within classroom management challenges (e.g., Chaw et al., 2021). Other studies referred to the decision-making processes in education, i.e., Skubiak (2021).

In the end, none of the studies were included in the review since none referred explicitly to our research question and study theme, i.e., Romanian preschool management's challenges during the Covid-19 pandemic (see Fig.1.).

Fig.1. Findings related to the inclusion criteria (Prisma chart)

Conclusion

Our research addresses the management challenges and opportunities in a COVID-19 post-pandemic reality, highlighting that extensive research is needed to understand better and manage the various and complex challenges managers of preschool education settings face in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the exploratory nature of the present paper raises several limitations, such as the number of databases consulted, and the fact that we did not account for the unpublished research. Given the recent events related to the pandemic, and the fact that this crisis health is far from being over, there are probably many studies undergoing a review process, that might be included in subsequent reviews, such as the present one. Nevertheless, this study is important as it raises awareness related to the scarce evidence concerning the management changes and challenges (and, maybe, opportunities as well), due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

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